

Magallanes Project: Testing the Marine Tidal Current Platform in the “Ría of Vigo”

Martech - Renewable Energy Session

16th June 2021 – 13:00 to 14:00

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The Magallanes Project

Marine Tidal Current Platform

The floating system called **ATIR** is based on a platform that incorporates a submerged part where two rotors are installed.

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Marine Tidal Current Platform

Name	Atir
Rated power	1500 kW
Weight	350 t
Draft/Length/Breadth	25 m / 45 m / 6 m
Rotors	2 (counter-rotating)
Rotor diameter / Separation	19 m / 1 diameter
Rotor rated speed	17 rpm
Pitch	variable (0 to 270°)
Gearbox ratio	98
Generators	2×850 kW @ 690 V
Generators rated speed	1600 rpm
Converters	2×900 kW AC/AC

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Marine Tidal Current Platform

Blade pitch positions from feather to optimum pitch position for the two tidal current directions:

- I and IV represent full-feathered position
- II and V represent intermediate positions
- III and VI represent optimum pitch

Being I, II and III for the bow to stern current and IV, V and VI for the stern to bow current.

The Towing Test

Tidal current was **emulated** by towing the platform with a tugboat are analyzed. The tests were conducted in the Ria of **Vigo** (Northwest of Spain)

Tugboat

Draft / Length / Breadth	4 m / 23.4 m / 9.8 m
Gross register tonnage	273 t
Power	3752 HP
Bollard pull	54 t
Avg. Speed	5.7 kn
Max. Speed	11.2 kn

The **main differences** between these **tests** and **real working** conditions under tidal currents are as follows:

- During tides, the current speed decreases with depth; however, the speed profile during towing is almost constant.
- Waves, wind, and marine currents affect the test conditions.
- During the tests, the towline length was greater than 100 m to minimize the impact of the wake produced by the tugboat.
- The emulated tidal current depends on the tugboat operation; therefore, it is affected by the blade pitch and TSR of the rotors. Under real conditions, the current depends only on the tide.
- The platform showed a certain level of roll, pitch, and yaw during towing.

The Towing Test

The **power network** was emulated using an autotransformer (400 kVA; 690 V/400 V), a diesel generator (350 kW), and a bank of dump load resistors (600 kW)

The platform was operated in the same way that under real tidal currents, although with reduced rated power owing to the size of the dump loads

Electrical configuration during tests

Test Results

The results show that a power of approximately 400 kW was generated during the tests with a platform speed of approximately 5 knots (2.6 m/s).

Temporal evolution of several variables during towing tests (blue: rotor no. 1; red: rotor no.2)

Test Results

The full-feathered position refers to the blade position at which the rotor does not rotate at different current speeds. Its value is **between 92° and 94°**.

Test Results

The blades were mounted at sea. Then, it was necessary to obtain the values of the blade pitch for the **full-feathered** position and the **optimum** one that maximizes the power coefficient.

The blade pitch for the **optimum power coefficient** is the pitch at which, for a given marine current, the maximum power is generated.

$$c_{pr} = \frac{P_{gen}}{\frac{1}{2}Av^3} \quad \text{Power coefficient at generator side}$$
$$TSR = \frac{\omega R}{v_{\infty}} \quad \text{Tip Speed Ratio}$$

Drive Train Losses

Using data provided by the manufacturer, gearbox and generator performance was estimated.

Generator power losses in kW

speed [rpm]	Torque/ Rated Torque [%]				
	4%	16%	36%	64%	100%
300	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3
600	7.8	7.9	7.9	7.9	8.0
900	9.7	9.7	9.8	10.1	10.9
1200	11.7	11.8	12.2	13.5	16.1
1500	13.9	14.2	15.5	19.1	27.0

Power losses in the gearbox

Rotor Modelling

Power coefficient in the rotor side (c_{pr}) has been obtained by taking account estimated losses in gearbox and generator.

Power coefficient at the rotor (c_{pr}) and generator (c_{pg}) sides

Rotor Modelling

From a dimensional analysis of the blades, in which eighteen blade sections were considered, the rotor was modeled using the Blade Element Momentum (BEM) method implemented in XFOIL and MATLAB.

The model has been tuned using measurement results.

Values of c_{pr} as a function of the TSR and blade pitch

Where is Atir?

Nowadays, Atir is being tested at the Tidal Test Site of the EMEC (Orkney Islands).

Conclusions

- Data from towing test has been analyzed
- Losses in gearboxes, generators, and AC/AC converters have been estimated
- Estimation of the rotor behavior in terms of the TSR, blade pitch, and power coefficient using BEM techniques.

The control and measured variables are not completely under control in this type of tests. This makes obtaining the model parameters more challenging than in a laboratory.

In following studies, the interaction (wake) between rotors has been simulated. So, power curve can be obtained.

power curve

